

Effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on Error Types Committed in Algebra Among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed effects of cooperative learning strategy on error types committed in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria. Mixed method research design was adopted for the study. Thus, descriptive survey research design was employed to identify errors which led to the development of the instrument; and the quasi-experimental pretest, posttest control group design to establish the cause-and-effect between variables of the study. Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school mathematics students in Kano state. The instruments adapted from West African Examination Council (WAEC) past question papers were validated for data collection with Error Identification Test (EIT) and Algebra Performance Test (APT) with reliability coefficients of 0.68 and 0.74 respectively using Cronbach alpha reliability teste. While the experimental group was exposed to cooperative learning instructional treatment, the control group were exposed to traditional method. Three null hypotheses guided the study. Chi square (χ^2) and t-test statistics were used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The major findings of this study revealed senior secondary school students in Kano state do commit procedural, factual, conceptual and comprehension errors in algebraic and the CLIS is gender fair in remediating the problems. On the basis of these, it was concluded that CLIS is an effective tool for remediating students' errors in algebra. It was recommended that the CLIS should be encouraged in place of the conventional lecture method in teaching algebraic concepts at the senior secondary school level.

Keywords: Algebra, Cooperative Learning, Error, Frequency, Mathematics

Introduction

Mathematics is the branch of science that studies numbers, forms and their relationships. It is the science and study of quality, structure, space, and change that seeks out patterns, formulate new conjectures which are opinions based on incomplete evidence; and establish truth by rigorous deduction from appropriately chosen axioms (widely accepted opinion) and definitions. It is a pivot in which other sciences revolve and serves as a means of sharpening man's reasoning ability and developing personality (Agwagah, 2001). Mathematics is a vast and diverse field that encompasses various branches, each with its own unique focus and applications. These branches of mathematics include pure mathematics, applied mathematics, interdisciplinary mathematics among others. In fact, the branches are inexhaustible and there may be overlap between them. Being a scholarly domain, mathematicians build on each other's work and behave in ways that push the discipline forward. This progress contributes to scientific breakthroughs. However, algebra, which is the focus of this study according to Tarr & Knith, (2013) is a branch of mathematics that uses letters to represent numbers. An algebraic expression is made up of three things: numbers, variables (letters) and operations such as $-$ or $+$. These may, in turn, be connected with equality sign to form algebraic statements such as $3y = 12$, $2y + 4x = 10$, $7y - 4 = 3x$ (Keller, 2007). This is the bone of contention in the teaching of mathematics in Nigerian secondary schools.

Mathematics plays a vital role in the learning and understanding of the principles applied to other sciences (Clements, 2014). For instance, mathematics provides the language and tools to measure and understand scientific concepts just as technology applies scientific and mathematical principles to develop useful tools and systems. In fact, science study of the natural world relies on mathematics. In other words, mathematics helps achieve a deeper understanding of scientific concepts, providing ways to quantify and explain scientific relationships; in the field of physics, mathematics is used to describe and model the behavior of matter and energy; in chemistry, it is used to analyze chemical reactions and predict the properties of different substances; while in computer science, it is used to develop algorithms (set of rules) and write code that powers our digital world (Wiles 2007). That is how vast and important mathematics is to the new world. Thus, concept formation, abstraction, generalization, theory-building and problem solving which are basic mathematical activities are also integral part of the problem-solving process.

However, teaching of mathematics to young people in secondary schools has been very tiring, cumbersome and uninteresting because of the methods used to impart such exquisite knowledge. Traditionally, the lecture method was the

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dominating approach that has been used over the years to teach mathematics to school children. This, Okpala & Anene (2009) observed has been highly traditional and teacher-centered; while Odili (2005) sees it as a major problem that militates against students understanding of mathematics and mathematical concepts in schools, thereby contributing to poor performance output in internal and external examinations. The traditional lecture method, which had hitherto been used over decades, is concerned with the teacher being the controller of the learning environment. Power and responsibility were held by the teacher and they play the role of instructor (lecture) and decision maker on curriculum content. According to Inah (2014), the lecture method allows the teacher to deliver large amount of information in a short time with the capacity for routine repeatability for new groups of students.

In furtherance of this general assertion, the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008) advocates teaching method that is activity-oriented, expository and experimental. If the citizens of the country will compete favourably with their counterparts in this 21st century global village of advanced science, technology and mathematics, the teaching and learning of mathematics at the secondary school level should be repositioned because it is another foundation upon which other levels of education are built. In the light of the above, it is important to lay solid foundation in mathematics by using activity-oriented methods which are learner-centered to teach the subject. A number of activity-oriented strategies, according to Lawal (2009) have been advocated for curriculum designers and science educators to help improve on the failure rate in mathematics among secondary school students. One of the activity-based strategies is the cooperative learning instructional strategy, described by Eniaiyaju (2010) as a discovery method in which small groups are used. It is generally understood to be learning which takes place in an environment where students work collaboratively in small groups by sharing ideas while working on a given task. This learning strategy, according to Slaven (2013) allows students in small groups to communicate with each other and it is believed that dialogue aids learning and goal-oriented (Wiles 2007). The characteristics among others, are positive interdependence, face-to-face interaction, social skills, shared leadership, collaborative problem solving, mutual support and teacher facilitation.

In order to effectively implement the cooperative learning in the classroom, the following processes stages, according to Olanrewaju (2012), must be succinctly established: i. state clear goals and expectations of the outcome of topics being taught; ii. train students in cooperative learning skills; iii. choose the suitable cooperative learning strategy to be employed; iv. monitor and provide appropriate feedback as the class progresses; v. encourages student reflection and self-assessment. By incorporating cooperative learning into teaching practices, the teachers can create supportive and inclusive learning environment that promotes academic achievement, social skills and team work. In this way, errors committed by students will be brought to the barest minimum. This strategy involves dividing the class into small groups of 3-5 pupils of varying ability such that it encourages group members to seek assistance from each other; and in which every member accepts responsibility for the entire team (Gowers, 2002). However, the cooperative learning session must commence with students given practice on cooperative work; problems that elicits cooperation. (Sarah & Cassidy, 2006; Wendy, 2005). Students are encouraged to use one activity sheet, work at their own pace with no time constraint; however, when a team concludes a task another activity sheet is released to them. They are encouraged to pose questions to members, check and clarify thoughts, agree and conclude on the response to record on the activity sheet. The main task of the teacher is to constantly remind the group members of helping their group to succeed through dialogue, attentiveness and making inputs to discussion.

Despite the efforts put in by mathematics teachers in ensuring the right concepts are taught, no matter the methodology hiccups, errors committed in mathematics have become rampant among secondary school students in Kano state schools (Odili, 2005). These errors or mistakes, as they are popularly called, are used interchangeably because they stand for incorrect concepts, ideas of misguided information, but differ in their levels of incorrectness. According to Salman, (2004), a mistake has the characteristics of being corrected when challenged, but an error does not possess such characteristics. Topson (1999) posited that error in mathematics context is the difference between the value of an appropriation or estimation and the true value. He stressed further that error may or may not have a plus (+) or minus (-) sign attached to indicate whether a number is too big or too small. Error analysis, therefore, is a method commonly used to identify the causes of students' mistakes by reviewing the students' work and then look out for patterns of misunderstanding. Students' errors may be caused by semantic differences between mathematical language and natural language by individual differences in spatial abilities, by deficiencies in mastery of prerequisites, by incorrect association of failure of cognitive control, and by the application of irrelevant strategies or rules (Steve, 2002). It is in recognition of the foregoing that this study assessed the effects of cooperative learning strategy in remedying the frequency of, and error types committed in algebra by secondary school students in Kano state.

Statement of the Research Problem

Algebra is a fundamental subject in mathematics, but students often struggle with it due to various errors and misconceptions. Despite the importance of algebra, research has shown that students make frequent errors particularly in areas as equation solving, graphing and functional operations (Cohen & Lotan, 2014). However, cooperative learning has been shown to be an effective instructional strategy in promoting students understanding. Recognizing this, the study aims to investigate the effectiveness of cooperative learning in rectifying and types of errors in algebra. Errors in algebra can be persistent and difficult to correct, particularly when students are taught with the traditional method. Cooperative learning offers a promising alternative, as it allows students to work together, share ideas, and learn from one another. Although there is paucity of research on the effectiveness of cooperative learning in reducing the frequency and types of errors in algebra (Tarr & Knuth, 2013). This study aims to address this gap by investigating the impact of cooperative learning on algebra errors. Teachers often struggle to identify and address errors in algebra, particularly in large and diverse classrooms. Cooperative learning has been shown to promote student engagement and motivation (Cohen & Lotan, 2014), but its potential to support teachers in identifying and addressing errors is not well-explored. This study, therefore, assessed effects of cooperative learning strategy on error types committed in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State
2. To determine if there is difference in the types of errors committed while solving algebraic problems between male and Female senior secondary school students in Kano State
3. To determine the impact of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State

Research Questions

1. What are the frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State?
2. What is the difference in mean scores in the types of errors committed while solving algebraic problems between male and Female senior secondary school students in Kano State?
3. What are the impacts of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Hypotheses

This study tested the following hypotheses at $p \leq 0.05$

- H₀₁. There are no significant differences in frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State
- H₀₂. There is no significant difference between male and female students while solving algebraic problems in Kano State
- H₀₃. There is no significant impact of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State

Methodology

This study assessed effects of cooperative learning strategy on error types committed in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria. The mixed method research design adopted for the study included descriptive survey research design to identify errors which led to the development of the instrument; and the quasi-experimental pretest, posttest control group design to establish the cause-and-effect between variables of the study. Population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school mathematics students in Kano state; and sample was taken from the six (6) schools that met the two conditions of availability of qualified mathematics teachers and infrastructural facilities; hence, exposed to error identification test (EIT). Based on this test, only two (N=2) coeducational that were not significantly different in the EIT were used as samples for the study. This instrument, adapted from the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) question papers (2007 – 2011) and used to identify errors committed by students in solving algebraic problems, comprised of seventeen (17) test items of short essay

questions spread across the senior secondary school syllabus. The scripts were marked and errors recorded accordingly. In each of the sampled schools, the subjects were divided into experimental and control groups. The former was exposed to the cooperative learning strategy adapted from Kagan’s (1994) NHT instructional model while the latter group was handled by their regular classroom teacher using the lecture method. The teaching lasted for four (4) weeks after which the Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was administered on the subjects. Algebraic Performance Test (APT) used for this study was adapted from the WAEC past question papers (2007 – 2011) administered in pre-test and post-test forms, comprised of thirty (30) multiple choice items with four (4) options A-D, and seven (7) short essay questions. The EIT and APT were administered to the subjects as pretest and post-test to the two groups. The scripts for both pretest and post-test were marked based on the marking scheme and errors committed were recorded accordingly. Data collected were recorded and analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistics. All hypothesis were deemed significant at $P \geq 0.05$ alpha level.

Presentation of Results

The data collected from tests carried out on EIT and APT employed in this study were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentages, mean, standard deviation) and presented in line with the research questions and succinctly described; while the inferential statistics of t-test and Chi square were used to test the null hypotheses raised for the study. All hypotheses are deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level as presented in tables below:

Research Question 1:

1. What are the frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Table 1

Error Types	Pre-Test		Experimental		Post test		Experimental	
	Control		Freq	%	Control		Freq	%
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Procedural	32	13.0	34	15.1	31	13.7	28	21.3
Factual	24	9.8	14	6.2	23	10.2	9	6.87
Conceptual	40	16.3	37	16.4	33	14.6	10	7.63
Wrong operation	25	10.2	30	13.3	24	10.6	28	21.37
Defective algorithm	34	13.8	28	12.4	34	15.0	20	15.27
Misdirection	44	17.9	49	21.8	43	19.0	29	22.14
Comprehension	47	19.1	34	15.1	37	16.4	7	5.37
Total	246	100.0	226	100.0	226	100.0	131	100.0

Summary of frequency of error types committed by students in algebra

Source: Field Survey (2024)

A careful study of Table 1 above revealed the frequencies and percentages of error types committed by the students in the sampled schools before and after the experiment. The pre-test results showed that Comprehension (47;19.1%) and Misdirection (49;21.8%) were the most frequently committed errors in the control and experimental groups respectively while the post-test values recorded Misdirection (43;19.0% and 29; 22.14%) in both the control and experimental groups respectively. Although it was observed that variability in frequency of types of errors exist in both groups, it was higher in control (246; 226) than in experimental (226; 131) groups. These observations provided solutions to the first research question which sought to identify the frequency of error types committed by secondary school students in solving algebraic problems in the sampled schools. However, in order to test whether these observed frequencies are significant, the inferential statistics of Chi square was employed for analysis and the results are presented in Table 2.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁. There are no significant differences in frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State

Table 2

Summary of Chi square analysis on frequency of error types committed by control and experimental groups in senior secondary school algebra.

Error Types	Groups		Total
	Control	Experimental	
Procedural	32(34.40)	34(31.60)	66
Factual	24(19.81)	14(18.19)	38
Conceptual	40(40.13)	37(36.87)	77
Wrong operation	25(28.67)	30(26.33)	55
Defective algorithm	34(32.31)	28(29.69)	62
Misdirection	44(48.47)	49(44.53)	93
Comprehension	47(42.22)	34(38.78)	81
Total	246	226	472

$\chi^2_{(6)} = 5.36 < 0.05$ Not Significant Source: SPSS V10 Data Analysis software (2024)

The result presented in Table 2 revealed result of the chi square of observed value obtained from the control and experimental groups. Upon analysis, obtained chi square of 5.36 was less than the critical value ($\chi^2_{(6)} = P < 0.05$); therefore, the null hypothesis was retained. This implies that subjects in the two groups did not differ significantly in the frequency and type of errors they committed while solving algebraic problems before the experiment.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in mean scores in the types of errors committed while solving algebraic problems between male and Female senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Table 3

Summary of frequencies (F) and percentages (%) of error types committed in algebra by male and female students in Kano state

Error Types	Male		Female	
	Freq	%	Freq.	%
Procedural	13	21.0	15	21.7
Factual	4	6.5	5	7.2
Conceptual	3	4.8	7	10.1
Wrong operation	15	24.2	13	18.8
Defective algorithm	12	19.4	8	11.6
Misdirection	12	19.4	17	24.6
Comprehension	3	4.8	4	5.8
Total	62	100.0	69	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 3 reveals a relatively equal error types committed by the male and female subjects exposed to the cooperative learning strategy experiment. A careful study of the frequencies reveals that the trend of the errors basically followed the same pattern although the actual counts differ. There is a proportional occurrence of the errors in both groups; particularly when procedural errors (21.0% and 21.7%) for males and females were considered respectively. In order to find out if these differences are significant, the Chi square statistic was used for the analysis and the results are presents in Table 4.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₂. There is no significant difference between male and female students while solving algebraic problems in Kano State

Table 4

Summary of Chi square analysis on error types committed in algebra by male and female subjects after exposure to the cooperative learning strategy

Error types committed	Male	Female	Total
Procedural	13(13.47)	15(14.53)	28
Factual	4(4.33)	5(4.67)	9
Conceptual	3(4.81)	7(5.19)	10
Wrong operation	15(15.39)	13(16.61)	28
Defective algorithm	12(10.58)	8(11.42)	20
Misdirection	12(12.02)	17(12.98)	29
Comprehension	3(2.40)	4(2.60)	7
Total	62	69	131

$\chi^2_{(6)} = 2.53 < 0.05$ Not Significant Source: SPSS V10 Data Analysis software (202)

Table 4 is a summary of Chi square analysis of error scores committed by gender (M/F) before they were exposed to the effect of cooperative learning as a remedy in order to find out if there is gender specificity in error committed. Results obtained did not reveal significant difference ($\chi^2_{(6)} = P < 0.05$) between male and female subjects in the error committed while solving algebraic problems after the experiment. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained. This means the cooperative learning strategy was gender fair.

Research Question 3:

3. What are the impacts of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Table 5:

Summary of error types committed by percentages in control and experimental groups while solving algebraic problems

Error Types	Control		Experimental	
	Freq	%	Freq.	%
Procedural	32	13.0	34	15.1
Factual	24	9.8	14	6.2
Conceptual	40	16.3	37	16.4
Wrong operation	25	10.2	30	13.3
Defective algorithm	34	13.8	28	12.4
Misdirection	44	17.9	49	21.8
Comprehension	47	19.1	34	15.1
Total	246	100.0	236	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2024)

As shown in Table 5, errors of misdirection (experimental) and comprehension (control) had the highest frequencies; while the lowest was factual error in both control and experimental groups. Although the frequencies do not follow any corresponding pattern, higher errors committed in the control group are in comprehension, defective algorithm, conceptual and factual, while the experimental group recorded higher frequencies in procedural, wrong operation and misdirection when the two groups are juxtaposed. In other words, there is variability in the frequencies of error types as shown in Table 5. In order to find out if these error values are significant, the Chi square statistics was used for analysis. The results are presented in Table 6.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₃. There is no significant impact of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State

Table 6

Chi square analysis of error types before and after the cooperative learning strategy in the experimental group

Error types committed	Before	After	Total
Procedural	34(39.25)	28(22.75)	62
Factual	14(14.56)	9(8.44)	23
Conceptual	37(29.75)	10(17.25)	47
Wrong operation	30(29.21)	28(21.28)	58
Defective algorithm	28(30.39)	20(17.61)	48
Misdirection	49(49.38)	29(28.62)	78
Comprehension	34(25.96)	7(15.04)	41
Total	226	131	357

$$\chi^2_{(6)} = 17.44 \leq 0.05 \quad * \text{ Significant}$$

A careful study of Table 6 revealed the result of experiment for remediating identified errors in algebra using the cooperative learning strategy the subjects were expose to. There were recorded reduction in errors across all error types which could be attributed to the efficacy of the strategy used in the experiment, hence, the null hypothesis was rejected ($\chi^2_{(6)} = 17.44 \leq 0.05$). It could be affirmed that the cooperative learning strategy have caused this significant impact in remedying errors committed in algebra.

However, a further assessment of the impact of the cooperative learning strategy on the gender differences in error committed in algebra using the post test scores of male and female subjects, results of the t-test statistics employed was summarized in Table 7.

Table 7

Summary of t-test analysis of post-test scores of male and female subjects in the experimental group.

Gender	N	X ± SD	SE	X Gain	t-value	df	t-Crit	P	Rmk
Male	33	43.47+10.14	1.85	5.71	2.001	61	2.000	0.05	* Sig
Female	30	49.18+12.33	2.15						
Total	63	92.65+22.47	4.00						

$$t_{(62)} = 2.00 \leq 0.05 \quad * \text{ Significant}$$

In Table 7, the observed t-value of 2.001 in the test was higher than the critical value of t (2.000); and at df=61 and 0.05 alpha level, it implies that significant difference exists between the two means. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected by gender; as the female subjects performed better in the post-test analysis.

Discussion of Findings

It is common knowledge that errors abound in every human action and mathematics is not exempted. However, errors in algebra can be persistent and difficult to correct particularly when students are taught in a traditional manner (Davidson, 2017). Based on this assertion, this study assessed the effects of cooperative learning strategy in remedying frequency and error types in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state. Cooperative learning is a teaching strategy that enables students to work together in small groups in order to achieve common goals. In line with this, three variables selected for this study focused on frequency of error types, treatment and impact of treatment by gender. Error types, it was observed, were more frequent during the pre-test in comprehension and conceptual (control group; 40 and 47 respectively), misdirection (experimental; 49); whereas post-test value errors in the experiment group have misdirection (29) as the highest error frequency. This result is in line with Lawal, (2009) observation that when effective remediation is effected, meaningful learning would be achieved. Results of chi-square analysis on types of errors committed in the process of solving algebraic problems was not significant when the control and experimental groups were compared. This is consistent with the findings of Salman (2004) who affirmed that students do commit errors at non-significant rates while

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identifying types of errors committed in specific topics and concepts in algebra. The types of errors committed by subjects in the experimental group before and after treatment, when compared, revealed after chi-square statistical analysis that observed errors before (226) was higher than observed errors after (131) exposure to the cooperative learning strategy. This finding agrees with that of Swanson (2000) who pointed out that cooperative learning approach can bring positive results in deeper understanding of content, increased overall achievement in grades, improved self-esteem and higher motivation to remain on task. This finding also agrees with Solomon (2002) that besides helping students to become actively and constructively involved in content and developing team work skills, teachers also promote collaborative experiences and enhanced interpersonal relations with teams. Furthermore, Aiyede (2007) emphasized the advantages of the cooperative learning strategy as one through which understanding can become explicit in diverse ways that promote positive attitude

When the frequency and types of errors committed was tested by gender did not reveal any significant difference when the type and number of errors committed while solving algebraic problems were considered. This portrays the use of cooperative learning strategy as gender fair. This finding agrees with the report of Baer (2005) who reported that most of the studies done on cooperative learning placed students on heterogenous groups; and Adeniyi (2000) rather ascribes low performance to ineffective teaching with the traditional methods.

Furthermore, results of chi square analysis of error types before and after the cooperative learning strategy in the experimental group was significant ($t_{(62)} = 2.00 \leq 0.05$); while the same significant result ($t_{(62)} = 2.00 \leq 0.05$) was recorded by gender when post treatment test was considered. This gender difference was in favour of the females ($N=30$; $X+SD=49.18+12.33$) compared to their male counterparts ($N=33$; $X+SD=43.47+10.14$) who recorded higher scores in the experiment. the efficacy of the cooperative learning strategy which was the main instrument used as treatment for this study cannot be waived aside as this result is in agreement with results of earlier studies (Eniayēju, 2010; Olanrewaju, 2012; Vermette, 2004). Recognizing that the results of this study agree with global best practices in using the cooperative learning strategy as an effective instructional approach because of apparent learner involvement, sustained motivation, positive attitudes, improved social skills and accommodation of heterogeneity (Gillies and Boyle, 2006), there is need for all mathematics teachers to begin to employ this method in teaching algebra, if they have not started.

Conclusion

This study was carried out to investigate the effects of cooperative learning in remedying frequency and error types in algebra by secondary school students in Kano state. The findings of this study reveal that senior secondary school students generally committed similar error types which are not significantly different by gender while involved in solving algebraic problems; and these errors types can be reduced by using cooperative learning strategies. The results are consistent with previous research outcomes. It is concluded that the procedure of the strategy has positive effects on students' morale and social interaction.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been proffered based on the findings of this study:

1. Teachers should endeavor to identify common types of errors students commit while solving algebraic problems in mathematics
2. When there is need to reduce identified errors, the use of cooperative learning strategy should be encouraged
3. Cooperative learning strategy should be used in teaching algebraic problems at the senior secondary school level.
4. Curriculum development research bodies such as the Nigerian Educational and Research Development Council should emphasize the use of cooperative learning strategy as a method of teaching in schools.
5. Science professional bodies like the Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) and the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize regular workshops on the modus operandi of the cooperative learning strategy as a method of teaching and learning.

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